

SEMANTIC GENDER SYSTEM OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation: This article discusses the specifics of the gender system in English, its semantic aspects.

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Introduction

Language may influence the perception and recall of things and events through many aspects of its structure. One source of influence is through systems of classification. Any lexical or grammatical marker constitutes a classifier if it has a greater than chance correlation with semantic determinants or with determinants in the social situation of speech. The lexical contrast of "man" vs. "woman" is a classifier for a semantic difference, and the choice is predictable if we control the referent, by asking informants to name people or pictures of men and women. The contrast of "cat" vs. "kitty" is a classifier correlated with social determinants, and the choice is predictable if we control the audience of speech.

Materials and methods

It has been demonstrated clearly by Brown and Lenneberg that a system of lexical classification, English color terminology, systematically influences memory. Such a lexical system is explicit in its semantic correlates, and lexical selections have minimum predictability from the utterance structure alone¹.

Results and discussion

Many grammatical markers also have semantic correlates-English plurality, for example. The peculiarity of such grammatical, in contrast to lexical, classification is that it may be mandatory even when there is no appropriate semantic or social cue, or when the feature is of minimal importance to the speaker. Thus its semantic associations may be attenuated. If the correlation is perfect, the learning of the linguistic contrast may encourage earlier learning of the associated referential discrimination. Casagrande's finding that young Navaho-speaking children were more likely than were English-speaking Navaho children in the same community to sort objects on the basis of form, is an example of the influence of a completely consistent classification system, the Navaho verb stems.

¹ Kvetko, P. English Lexicology. Trnava : Univerzita Sv. Cyrila a Metoda, 2015. 203 p., ISBN: 80-89220-16-9.

A correlation that is less than perfect may both stimulate the learning of referential discriminations and influence the connotations of the exceptional items. English form classes such as mass nouns and verbs are examples of a less than perfect semantic correlation. Brown has pointed out that a higher proportion of the conversation of children concerns the tangible, visible world, and that, in their speech, form classes may have greater semantic consistency than in adult speech. He gave children non-sense words in various linguistic environments, such as "a sib", "some sib," and "sibbing," and demonstrated systematic choice of pictures in accordance with the linguistic markers. Thus pictures of confetti-like heaps were chosen as "some sib," contoured simple objects as "a sib," and pictures of actions as "sibbing." ³ Thus the meaning of ambiguous items-the nonsense words-was influenced by the dominant features of meaning of the grammatical class to which they belonged.

Gender is an instance of an imperfectly correlated grammatical system of classification. In many Indo-European languages the names of males belong to the masculine gender and of females to the feminine gender. Whether an animate-inanimate distinction is made varies with the language. We are concerned here with the assignment of meaning to new items. Presumably, the connotations of sex difference should generalize to members of the masculine and feminine classes, even if the referent is abstract or inanimate².

Gender systems differ in certain respects. There is considerable evidence in psychological research about the processes by which stimulus generalization and mediated generalization occur. We shall extend these conclusions to make certain predictions about the effects of differences in gender systems. Stimulus generalization refers to the extension to a new stimulus of a response learned to another stimulus. Thus, animals trained to approach, for food, or to avoid, because of shock, a door painted with a particular hue, will extend this response, without training, to doors with other hues. The more similar the hue the greater the transfer of the response.

On psychological grounds, we may make certain predictions about semantic generalization in grammar:

(1) The larger the proportion of items, in terms of frequency of usage, which share a specific and observable semantic correlate, the greater the generalization. Thus, in a two-gender system with masculine and feminine gender, many items will refer to inanimate objects with qualities irrelevant to sex. If a three-gender system places many of these inanimate referents in a

² Widdowson, H. G. *Linguistics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016. 135 p., ISBN: 0 19 437206 5

neuter class, a higher proportion of the masculine items may refer to males and more of the feminine items to females. In the latter system, generalization should be greater³.

(2) The less the overlap between classes, the stronger the generalization. By overlap is' meant manifestly inappropriate classification. Latin *poeta*, *agricola*, and *nauta* when they refer to males are syntactically masculine, but they follow a predominantly feminine declension. The same is true of Italian *il dentista*, *il poeta*, *il propheta*, *il artista*, *il messia*, which have the feminine final vowel. Since these nouns are syntactically masculine, the force of the deviation is somewhat vitiated. It would be expected that such cases, like deviant verb inflections, might survive only in frequent forms or in elite groups, since analogy would tend to suppress them in daily conversation. A few cases of complete overlap appear in Italian, in which a male referent is named by a feminine form which is also syntactically feminine: *la guida*, *la guardia*, and *la tigre*.

(3) Generalization is reduced if one of the classes is closed. In such a case new terms will be assigned to the open class regardless of the attributes of the referent. The effect of such a restriction would be to increase overlap between classes.

(4) The larger the number of markers of gender in an utterance related to a given item, the greater the generalization will be. If there is a phonetic similarity between the linguistic cues in the various markers, then those markers become more strongly related to the semantic contrast. In Italian the fact that both adjectives and nouns use -o vs. -a to mark gender strengthens the association of each with sex. It is in fact improbable that speakers could sustain a system in which phonetically similar morphemes were associated with male referents in a nominal form and female referents in a modifier. A few high-frequency exceptions might be tolerated but the tendency would be towards consistency.

Conclusion

Modern linguists have rightfully been critical of semantic assumptions which are either untested or untestable. Yet there are certain points in linguistic contact and change and in stylistic differentiation where semantic influences may be significant, and where formal analyses may be supplemented. We have shown that it is possible to test semantic statements about contemporary languages, believing that the systematic assessment of the semantic aspects of formal categories will prove to be important in the study of the uses of language.

³ Zwarts, J., Hogeweg, L., Lestrade, S., Malchukov, A. Semantic markedness in gender opposition, blocking and fossilization. *STUF - Language Typology and Universals*: Vol. 62, No. 4, (2009). pp. 325-343. ISSN: 1867-8319.

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